

Comprehensive Analysis of Artificial Organs and Perspectives on Their Development

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1. Abstract

In the modern world, artificial organs are expected to play a significant role in human health. Following that, biomedical engineering has been rapidly developing since the mid-20th century and continues to work on the innovations it offers the world today. However, the average person's understanding of this scientific field remains limited. The primary goal of this article is to educate the public and provide a general understanding of what artificial organs are and why they are a good alternative to organ donation. This review touches on the history of artificial organs and examines their types, mechanisms, and manufacturing methods. Another goal of this work is to determine the public's knowledge about artificial organs and their attitudes toward the potential transplantation of these organs. To address this, a study was conducted, and its results are presented in the section on the ethical aspects of artificial organs.

2. Introduction:

The rapid advancement of technology has significantly progressed the development of artificial organs, leading to their rapid integration into medical practice. Critical advancements have been made in developing new materials and manufacturing methods that could enhance artificial organs' general biocompatibility and lifetime. Unlike human organ transplants, artificial organ availability can streamline the transplantation process considerably, not requiring time for donor matching. Given these advancements, a comprehensive literature analysis has been conducted to explore newly developed manufacturing methods and compare commonly used materials such as metals, biopolymers, and artificially cultured cells. Also, we conducted the analysis of operating principles and clinical applications of various types of artificial organs based on specific needs. We also estimate potential challenges in the application of artificial organ transplantation. Finally, we present the results of a sociological survey that estimates public perceptions regarding artificial organs' utilization.

3. General information about artificial organs

3.1. Types of artificial organs

Depending on the way of manufacturing and the materials used, artificial organs are generally divided into 3 broad categories (X. Wang 2019).

Mechanical artificial organs do not contain any biomaterials and are fully composed of synthetic materials (particular kinds of modified plastic) and metals. The first transplanted artificial organs (heart and kidney), invented by Willem Kolf, were made of metal (Cooley 2009). Thus, mechanical artificial organs initiated the era of artificial organs. Although some of them may not completely mimic the internal organs of our body due to the properties of their materials, they are widely used to replace external organs such as missing limbs (prostheses of legs, feet, elbows, hands, etc.) and damaged or missing bones or joints (titanium plates for cranioplasty of the skull (Aydin et al. 2011), artificial knee joint (Bargir, Phafat, and Sonkamble 2023), etc.)

Biomechanical artificial organs combine particular mechanical and biological properties due to the presence of both mechanical (metal or plastic parts) and living (cells, etc.) in their structures.

Biological or bioartificial organs are made of artificially synthesized biodegradable biopolymers or living cells. In contrast to mechanical organs, they are not as durable and, similarly to human organs, are more exposed to the influence of the body's inner processes. However, they are less likely to cause immunological reactions of rejection after transplantation into a human body (Praveena et al. 2024). No less important is the tendency to manufacture artificial organs using the principles of physiology of corresponding organs to ensure the effect of mimicry. This approach makes it possible to create bioartificial organs that the organism cannot distinguish from the usual ones, avoiding rejection or non-acceptance reactions (Praveena et al. 2024).

3.2. Classification of organ manufacturing technologies

Depending on the processing mechanism, bioartificial organ manufacturing technologies can be classified into three groups (X. Wang 2019):

Two-nozzle 3D bioprinting — utilizes bio-inks, which can be different types of cells encapsulated within a supportive matrix. To mimic the complexity of real tissues often requires multiple bio-inks. For example, we need endothelial cells (lining the vessel) and smooth muscle cells (for the vessel wall) to print a blood vessel. Traditional bioprinters use more than one print head to switch between different bio-inks during the printing process (X. Wang 2019). In two-nozzle 3D bioprinting, a single printhead with two interchangeable nozzles allows us to switch between different bio-inks seamlessly and minimize the transition distance when switching from one bio-ink to another, maintaining accuracy and structural integrity.

Additive combined molding — includes inside-out heterogeneous cell integration patterns in a layer-by-layer increasing manner. It is a typical semi-automated inside-out engineering technique regarding the predefined scale-up molds (X. Wang 2019). This method is very accurate and easily eradicates the immune response. As it is model-dependent, matrices are necessary.

Decellularized organ regeneration — isolates the extracellular matrix (ECM) of tissue while completely removing its inhabiting cells. The organ is treated with chemicals or detergents to dissolve all the cells inside, leaving behind a scaffold made of the organ's natural material. The resulting ECM scaffold retains the natural composition of the original tissue. Decellularized ECM preserves the natural microenvironment features essential for tissue function, offering better biocompatibility than synthetic compounds. The ECM scaffold retains cell attachment sites, allowing seeded cells to adhere and grow (MacNeil 2023).

3.3. Aspects of applying the materials for manufacturing artificial organs

Artificial organs' functioning principles are tailored to their specific type and the materials employed.

The functioning of **mechanical artificial organs** completely bounds to the characteristics of metals (such as iron, titanium, aluminium, stainless steel, and gold) and smaller amounts of other inorganic polymers (such as carbon-, nitrogen- and oxygen-containing compounds) (Larry L. Hench 2005) which were used for manufacturing and the applied technological schemes during the process of manufacturing (X. Wang 2019). By this, individuals avoid using only one certain type of metal, applying the correlation of metals' content in their alloys to meet all the requirements for certain artificial organs.

The application of artificial organs is strictly restricted by the biocompatibility of the materials from which they are made (X. Wang 2019). In contradiction to biomaterials, neither metals nor other inorganic materials are biodegradable. Nonetheless, simultaneously with low indicators of compatibility of metals and other inorganic compounds, these materials demonstrate the high strength of their fibers, the ability to endure harsh strain, and a noticeable resistance to physical deformations. One of the properties that conditioned the spread applying of metals is their elastic deformation — the ability of a material to instantaneously return to primer dimensions, size, and form if the interaction time with outer factors was relatively short. Metal alloys and other inorganic compounds also demonstrate high electrical conductivity indicators, enabling us to apply these materials to the inner mechanisms of artificial organs.

Interestingly, some metal alloys can possess properties that allow them to return to their primary form through the shape memory effect. Among the alloys, the Nickel-titanium (Ni-Ti) alloys, sometimes called nitinol, most efficiently demonstrate this property. This peculiarity allows the application of Ni-Ti for medical purposes, such as using these alloys for the fixation of broken bones or using Ni-Ti alloys in artificial kidney pumps.

Thus, we use mechanical artificial, when we prioritize physical properties, such as tensile strength, resistance to deformation, and abrasion resistance (Larry L. Hench 2005). This leads us to conclude that we can use artificial organs made of metal alloys and other inorganic

compounds for outer prosthetics of amputated limbs, where biocompatibility isn't demanded and physical properties are preferred. Also, we can utilize these materials to create the inner mechanism of biomechanical organs, where the outer part of an artificial organ that interacts straightforwardly with the human body is biocompatible.

Biological tissues and cells are highly used for manufacturing **biological artificial organs**. Such organs show us incredibly high biocompatibility, biodegradability, and a low or almost absent immune reaction to organism rejection. Besides biological tissues and cells for manufacturing biological artificial organs, we might also use Biodegradable Scaffolds (such as collagen, chitosan, and gelatin), some synthetic biodegradable polymers (polylactic acid (PLA), polyglycolic acid (PGA), polycaprolactone (PCL), and polyethylene glycol (PEG))

Biomechanical artificial organs combine the peculiarities of bioartificial and mechanical organs. This hybrid kind can incorporate high indicators of physical properties, such as high tensile strength, resistance to fracture due to the influence of a high load of outer factors, etc. It can also reveal high measures of biocompatibility and biodegradability because of the particulate contents of biological materials. According to current observations, this category is the most applied in regenerative medicine because of enhanced functionality, compatibility, durability and longevity, self-repair and adaptation, and reduced immunosuppression.

4. Challenges of using artificial organs

4.1. Immunological reaction

It is mainly thought that bioengineered organs might escape immunological reactions because of the specific materials they are made of. However, antigens implanted in the body invariably cause a local immunological reaction, determined by several factors, including surface topography, chemical composition, speed of resorption, type of dissolution product, and mechanical properties. The fundamental principle is that a specific antibody will bind to a specific antigen. (Larry L. Hench 2005).

The immune responses to bioengineered organs can be classified based on the component of the organ that is being recognized by the immune system:

Cell-specific immune response: involves the host's immune response toward different progenitor cells used in developing bioengineered organs (Tripathi et al. 2023).

Immune response to nonself biological scaffolds: recognized as foreign substances by the immune system. As early as nanoseconds after implantation, the tissues, proteins from blood, and intestinal fluids are adsorbed to the surface of the biomaterial. This causes the activation of the complement system, coagulation cascade, platelets, immune cells and triggers an inflammatory response (Bose 2021).

Protein-specific immune response: involves modifying the amount or function of extracellular proteins in the immune system. This could be a response to the proteins present in the bioengineered organ or those produced as a result of the interaction between the organ and the host's immune system.

These immune responses could have significant implications for the successful integration and function of bioengineered organs in recipients. Although the immune response can be managed via immunosuppressant therapy in most cases, it is still a major problem.

4.3. Products of secretion

Secretion — is the production and release of a useful substance by a gland or cell. Products of secretions include the gastrointestinal tract, which secretes digestive enzymes and gastric acid; the lungs, which secrete surfactants; and sebaceous glands, which secrete sebum to lubricate the skin and hair.

Secretions of Natural Organs:

Digestive System: The digestive tract secretes mucus, which protects the stomach lining from acidic digestive juices and facilitates the passage of feces.

Respiratory System: The respiratory tract produces mucus to trap inhaled bacteria and particles, which are expelled through coughing or swallowing.

Endocrine System: Endocrine glands secrete hormones that regulate diverse bodily functions, such as growth, metabolism, and reproduction.

Secretion of Artificial Organs:

Encapsulating secretory cells within microbeads or capsules could allow for the controlled release of specific substances. Engineering biomimetic materials that mimic tissues' natural structures and functions could also enable artificial organs to secrete substances physiologically relevantly.

- An artificial pancreas could secrete insulin to regulate blood sugar levels, potentially addressing diabetes.
- An artificial liver could secrete bile to aid in digestion and bilirubin to eliminate toxins, potentially treating liver failure.
- Artificial kidneys could filter blood and remove waste products, providing a viable alternative for patients with kidney disease (Zalevsky and Abdulhalim 2014).

5. Innovations in the field of the creation of artificial organs

Kidney Innovations

An artificial kidney is a medical device developed to replace the functions of kidneys in people with chronic kidney failure (MacNeil 2023). It is a portable device intended to purify blood from excess water and dissolve substances and toxins in patients with kidney failure outside a medical facility.

One of the first prototypes was created by the German scientist Willem Kolff during World War II. Currently, there are several types of artificial kidneys:

- Wearable artificial kidney (WAK) systems. «The WAK can be ergonomically adapted to the patient's body for maximum comfort while being worn» (*Trending Issue: Innovations in Alternative Therapies to Dialysis (WAK 3.0) - Dr. Victor Gura 2022*).
- Portable hemodialysis systems: This is the most common type of artificial kidney, designed for home use. It consists of a dialyzer, blood circuit, dialysis solution, and control system; it provides mobility but requires connection to water and electricity.
- Dialysate regeneration systems: They clean and regenerate the dialysis solution used for multiple uses, reducing fluid consumption.
- Implantable bioartificial kidneys: experimental devices implanted in the patient's body and function similarly to a real kidney. Scientists are currently working on creating such a bioartificial kidney — it will consist of living nephrons (functional units of the kidney) placed in a biocompatible membrane.

Patients with kidney diseases today face a grim reality: most die within three years of starting dialysis. To address it, KidneyX has leveraged open innovation. Last fall, KidneyX launched the Artificial Kidney Prize, a competition to accelerate the development of artificial kidneys for human clinical trials. Phase 1, designed and managed by Luminary Labs, invited innovators to submit solutions that enhance the functionality, efficiency, and reliability of artificial kidneys (“Open Innovation” 2018). There were introduced winning projects, each receiving \$650,000:

- David Cooper, University of Alabama: Genetically engineered pig kidneys designed to reduce the likelihood of rejection.
- Imec USA Center for Nanoelectronics Design: A wireless system for toxin removal, suitable for implanted, wearable, portable, or bedside artificial kidneys.
- Makana Therapeutics: Genetically modified pig kidneys to increase the supply of transplantable organs by overcoming antibody barriers to xenotransplantation.
- University of California, San Francisco: An implanted bioartificial kidney enabling continuous blood processing and waste directing to the bladder, allowing freedom of movement.
- University of Washington Dialysis Innovation Center: A wearable continuous hemodialysis device providing greater mobility.
- American Kidney Research Corporation: A wearable artificial kidney that requires no water for filtration, significantly reducing device weight (Hibbard 2021).

Heart Innovations

An artificial heart is a technological device designed to support blood circulation. It replaces the biological heart, taking over the function of pumping blood through the circulatory system (Wikipedia contributors 2024a).

The concept of an artificial heart emerged in the 1960s, but only in the 1980s, American scientist Dr. Robert Jarvik developed one of the first fully implantable artificial hearts, the Jarvik-7 (“Robert Jarvik, MD on the Jarvik-7” 2016). Around the same time, Russian scientist Vladimir Demikhov performed the first successful implantation of an artificial heart in a human (Matskeplishvili 2017). The French company Carmat created a bioprosthetic heart using biological and synthetic materials in 2013, the efficiency of which was proved by numerous trials.

Under the term "artificial heart," the following technical devices are understood:

- Ventricular assist devices (VADs) implanted in the body, aimed to replace the heart muscle and improve the patient's quality of life (“Ventricular Assist Device (VAD),” n.d.).

- Artificial heart valves are materials used to replace damaged ones, often seen in severe heart diseases. A mechanical heart valve is usually more durable than a bioprosthesis but carries a higher risk of thrombosis formation on the metal surface (Vinmec.com 2024).
- Devices for enhancing the viability of implants, such as heart-specific extracellular matrices made from animal-derived bioinks or organ-specific decellularized extracellular matrix (dECM) (Kim et al. 2020).

A new kind of artificial heart that combines synthetic and biological materials, as well as sensors and software to detect a patient's level of exertion and adjust output accordingly, is set to be tested in patients at cardiac surgery centers in Europe and the Middle East. If the bioprosthetic device made by Paris-based Carmat ("Home" 2017) proves safe and effective, it could be used for patients waiting for heart transplants (Rojahn 2013)

- China announced a new artificial heart built on rocket technology, using magnetic and liquid levitation from a rocket system; it is expected to enter clinical trials in the coming years (PTI 2018).
- In Switzerland, researchers have developed a soft silicone heart using innovative 3D printing methods. It has left and right ventricles, pumps blood-like fluid, and weighs about the same as a natural human heart (Scutti 2017).
- Queensland researcher Daniel Timms' titanium mini-heart, small enough to fit into a child's chest but powerful to support an adult, has become a leader in artificial heart technology (Riches 2024).

Liver Innovations

Researchers at Texas A&M University have created an artificial liver using lab-grown human liver cells to perform detoxification and protein synthesis functions. This development could become an alternative to liver transplantation for patients with liver failure (Schattenberg 2022).

Lung Innovations

Scientists at the University of Pittsburgh have developed artificial lungs that can operate for extended periods without external power sources, a potential lifesaver for people needing

lung transplants (“Wearable Artificial Lung to Be Developed at Pitt Through \$3.4 Million Grant,” n.d.).

Pancreas Innovations

Medtronic has received FDA approval for its artificial pancreas, an implantable device that can automatically regulate insulin levels in patients with type 1 diabetes (Al Idrus 2017).

Sensory Organ Innovations

In the field of sensory organs, advances have been made in developing artificial retinas and cochlear implants. These devices use electrical stimulation to transmit sensory information to the brain, restoring patients' vision and hearing. For example, artificial retinas can help patients detect motion, locate objects, and follow pathways (University of Copenhagen - The Faculty of Health and Medical Sciences 2023), (MacNeil 2023).

Artificial Nerves and Brain-Computer Interfaces

Artificial nerves and brain-computer interfaces (BCIs) are also under development to compensate for spinal cord injuries and control paralyzed muscles. These technologies use signals synthesized from patients' brain and muscle activity to restore functions lost due to injury or disease (MacNeil 2023).

OpenWorm Project

The OpenWorm project aims to create a complete digital model of the *C. elegans* nematode, including its nervous system. This ambitious task could help us better understand the human brain and develop new treatments for neurological diseases (Wikipedia contributors 2024b).

6. Ethical problems

Biomedical technologies are rapidly evolving, causing new challenges in ethics. That's why there are 3 general moral principles:

- **Respect for autonomy:** the decision about using bioengineered organs must be made by the patient, without violence of his rights (Larry L. Hench 2005), (Łuków and Różyńska 2015).
- **Beneficence:** doing good or acting in the best interest of the patient (Larry L. Hench 2005), (Martin-Fumadó, Gómez-Durán, and Morlans-Molina 2020).
- **Justice:** similar cases should be treated alike. However, this is a concern because everyone has a unique genome, physiological processes, financial situations, and moral beliefs (Larry L. Hench 2005).

There are main reasons that cause ethical problems in using artificial organs:

1. The type of biomanufactured organ (mechanical, biomechanical, bioartificial) and specific materials it is made from (different metals, biopolymers, tissues): any kind of artificial organ will be an antigen to the recipient's body. That means that each of them has its pros and cons, but the main issue is the moral preferences of the recipient.
2. Patient safety and risk assessment: every manipulation with biomedical devices has some risks, which must be evaluated to ensure the safety of patients (National Research Council (US) Committee on the Experiences et al. 2003).
3. Informed consent and human testing: informing patients and participants about all aspects of participating in clinical trials and getting their consent (National Research Council (US) Committee on the Experiences et al. 2003).
4. Cloning tissues and stem cell research: the potential loss of genetic material and the mutations these technologies can bring to later generations haven't been studied yet because it is difficult to obtain the consent of donors for taking material for conducting clinical research (Vallero and Vallero 2014), (Hyun 2010).
5. Human enhancement: genetic manipulation and the development of prosthetic organs raises ethical questions about the definition of being human ("Challenges and Ethical Considerations in Biomedical Engineering," n.d.).
6. Accessibility and affordability: ensuring that medical technologies are accessible and affordable to all who need them ("Challenges and Ethical Considerations in Biomedical Engineering," n.d.).

7. Animal testing: preventing or reducing suffering in other species (Vallero and Vallero 2014).
8. Environmental impact: promoting sustainability, minimal impact of bioengineering products (“Challenges and Ethical Considerations in Biomedical Engineering,” n.d.).

We surveyed people from different countries, age groups, occupations, and levels of awareness of the research topic to find out how society feels about the ethical problems of biomedical engineering.

All the responders highly rate the importance of the type of materials used to create artificial organs. 65% indicate the privilege of using artificially grown (cultivated) cells, while 35% believe that biopolymers are a good source. No one rated metals as the best material.

Figure 1

Respondents were asked to indicate their trust level in using artificial organs. Their answers ranged from 1 to 10 (1—don't trust, 10—completely trust). Based on the diagram, we can see a wide range in trust levels in these medical developments.

Rate your trust level in the use of artificial organs (from 1 to 10)

Figure 2

Most surveyed individuals (75%) would agree to an artificial organ implantation.

Would you agree to an artificial organ transplant?

Figure 3

Many of the study participants indicated possible risks of using artificial organs for patients:

- The greatest risk is the immune system's reaction and the production of antibodies, and the issue of blood clotting during passage through artificial organs also increases.
- Although it may rarely be hazardous to human health, its positiveness is more than 70% because many professionals check it.
- The risk of using artificial organs from cultivated cells is low because the cells can be manipulated so that mutations can occur until the full organ is formed and transplanted.
- It has risks, but if it helps improve lifestyle, there is no problem.

- It might lead to a paralysis of some body parts.

Responders were asked whether the following situation is acceptable based on their opinion: when the latest medical developments do not have time to undergo all phases of the clinical research, they can be used with the patient's written consent.

Figure 4

There are assumptions about how these technologies can change humanity, such as helping save lives, giving some individuals heightened advantages instead of natural abilities, and making their lives better. However, they could have unintended consequences, such as evolving humans and rapidly advancing medical sciences and technology.

There are ideas for overcoming specific ethical issues regarding artificial organs, such as spreading awareness and making access to these resources equal for everyone, state programs with financial assistance, volunteer funds, and international organizations.

According to survey findings, the material type of artificial organs plays an important role, and each has certain risks. The trust level in using artificial organs varies from 1 to 10, and most responses are from 4 to 8. The bigger part of survey participants indicate their agreeableness to an artificial organ transplant. There are many responses about the possible risks of using such medical developments when they did and didn't pass all stages of clinical research. However, some are inclined to believe that in the future, these technologies can improve human life and further the evolution of science.

To overcome ethical problems in biomedical engineering, society must be widely informed about available medical technologies, access to them should be equal to everyone, international and state programs with financial assistance must be launched, and volunteer funds must be collected.

7. Conclusion

This research paper summarizes the primary information about technologies for artificial organ manufacturing and the challenges of implementing their usage in society from comprehensive literature and sociological survey analysis.

Artificial organs are classified according to materials, manufacturing techniques, belonging to specific systems of organs, and other factors. The choice of a certain kind of artificial organ depends on the range of preferred qualities and functions expected to be executed.

Due to the complexity of the human body and the variety of physiological processes, the usage of artificial organs may be limited. The main challenge of organ transplantation is the immunological reaction. Furthermore, the lifespan of artificial organs depends highly on their specific type and the materials used. While many last up to 10 years, ongoing research aims to extend this. Various factors can shorten the lifespan of implants, including wear and tear, infections, blood clot formation, rejection by the body, and material degradation due to corrosion.

The secretions produced by artificial organs play a central role in their function and interaction with the body. They can affect the organ's functions, its interaction with other body systems, and the patient's overall health. Therefore, to further improve artificial organs, it is necessary to study the processes of secretion and their regulation in detail and assess the potential risks.

Innovations in biomedical engineering are taking a huge step away from today's donor dependence and revolutionizing medicine by offering new treatment methods. Advances such as tissue bioprinting, stem cell utilization, and improved biomaterials bring us closer to creating more durable artificial organs, opening up possibilities for improving the quality of life for patients suffering from severe diseases.

Implementing biomedical advancements in our lives raises a series of ethical dilemmas. An international survey was conducted to estimate individuals' opinions on these problems. Our main findings are presented in the figures above. Mainly, there is a lack of information regarding research topics, which leads to low awareness of ethical concepts. So, there is a

need to carry out public informational work, develop organ manufacturing technologies, and influence local authorities to make financial programs, helping people have equal access to medical advancements.

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